

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

**WP4 Pilot deployment, monitoring, and
co-evaluation**

María Calera, María-Llanos López, Anna Osann

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 130709.

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© DIANA Consortium, 2017

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	130709	Acronym	DIANA	
Full Title	Detection and Integrated Assessment of Non-authorized water Abstractions using EO			
Horizon 2020 Call	EO-1-2016: Downstream applications			
Type of Action	Innovation Action			
Start Date	1 st January 2017	Duration	36 Months	
Project URL	www.diana-h2020.eu			
Document URL	-			
EU Project Officer	Iulia SIMION			
Project Coordinator	Polimachi Simeonidou, Anna Osann			
Deliverable	D4.3 Co-evaluation and validation report (1)			
Work Package	WP4 – Pilot deployment, monitoring, and co-evaluation			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M24	Actual	M24
Nature	R – Report	Dissemination Level	CO/PU	
Lead Beneficiary	AgriSat			
Lead Author	María Calera	Email	maria.calera@agrisat.es	
	AgriSat	Phone	+34 967 033401	
Other authors	María-Llanos López, Anna Osann (AgriSat)			
Contributors	Pilot area teams			
Reviewer(s)	Massimo Natalizio (Sannio Alifano) and Carlo De Michelle (Ariespace)			
Keywords	Water abstractions monitoring, co-evaluation, pilot campaign, Earth observation, drought monitoring, drought forecast, WFD implementation support, co-evaluation			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
V00		Draft		AgriSat
V01		Final for review		AgriSat
V02	29/11/2019	Draft	Reviewer's comments included	AgriSat
V03	02/12/2019	Final to upload		AgriSat and reviewers

Index

List of Tables.....	4
List of Figures.....	5
Executive summary	6
1. Introduction.....	8
1.1. Purpose and scope of the document	8
1.2. Context of DIANA users and services	9
1.3. The nine steps of pilot deployment and co-evaluation.....	9
2. The DIANA pilot deployment and campaign execution	12
2.1. The concept of pilot deployment, campaigns and Core Users.....	12
2.2. Pre-campaign implementation and execution (2017)	14
2.3. Pilot campaign implementation and execution (2018).....	15
2.4. Validation campaign implementation and execution (2019).....	19
3. The DIANA co-evaluation and validation process	21
3.1. Verification	21
3.2. Participatory service evaluation and validation	23
3.2.1. Conclusions from regional meetings with end-users	25
3.2.2. Workflow of the DIANA platform in water management	28
4. Conclusions.....	35
References.....	36
Annexes	37
Annex A. Summarize of co-evaluation process in D4.3	37
Annex B. Comparison of classification by EO-data (Remote Sensing) versus field information in Bajo Jalón (Spain)	41
Annex C. List of Assistants to Regional Meeting.....	44

List of Tables

TABLE 1. DIANA CORE USERS (FROM D1.2).	13
TABLE 2. DIANA LEVEL 1 INFORMATION PRODUCTS.....	15
TABLE 3. PILOT AREAS CURRENTLY INCLUDED IN THE DIANA PLATFORM.	15
TABLE 4. PRODUCTS FROM PILOT AREAS UPLOADED TO DIANA PLATFORM.....	17
TABLE 5. PRODUCT GENERATED PER PILOT AREA AND UPLOADED INTO THE PLATFORM.	19
TABLE 6. TABLE PROVIDED TO THE PILOT AREAS TO CHECK ALL THE FUNCTIONALITIES OF THE PLATFORM.	20
TABLE 7. REGIONAL MEETING ORGANIZED DURING THE 3RD YEAR OF THE PROJECT IN THE PILOT AREA.	25

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

TABLE 8. TABLE OF AVERAGE CONSUMPTION OF IRRIGATION WATER ACCORDING TO THE MANAGEMENT RULES FOR THE 2017 CAMPAIGN*.....	30
TABLE 9. TABLE OF AVERAGE CONSUMPTION OF IRRIGATION WATER ACCORDING TO THE MANAGEMENT RULES FOR THE 2018 CAMPAIGN*.....	31
TABLE 10. TABLE OF AVERAGE CONSUMPTION OF IRRIGATION WATER ACCORDING TO THE MANAGEMENT RULES FOR THE 2019 CAMPAIGN*.....	32
TABLE 11. PARTICIPANTS IN THE 1 ST ROUND OF QUESTIONNAIRES ABOUT THE DIANA PLATFORM.....	37
TABLE 12. IDEAS FROM THE FIRST STEPS IN THE CO-EVALUATION AND THE STATUS OF THE IMPROVEMENTS.	37
TABLE 13. SUMMARY OF THE OPINIONS ABOUT THE PLATFORM FUNCTIONALITIES.....	38
TABLE 14. WATER ABSTRACTION SERVICE EVALUATION BY THE USERS.	39
TABLE 15. DROUGHT MONITORING SERVICE EVALUATION BY THE USERS.....	39
TABLE 16. GENERAL COMMENTS AND SUGGESTIONS BY THE USERS.	40
TABLE 17. RECLASSIFICATION TO MAKE THE COMPARISON BETWEEN DIANA CLASSIFICATION VERSUS FIELD INFORMATION. ...	42
TABLE 18. COMPARISON BETWEEN DIANA CLASSIFICATION BY REMOTE SENSING (RS) VERSUS FIELD WORK.....	43
TABLE 19. COMPARISON FOR THE VINEYARD CLASSIFICATION (IRRIGATED AND NON-IRRIGATED) BY REMOTE SENSING (RS) VERSUS FIELD WORK.	43
TABLE 20. LIST OF ASSISTANTS ORGANIZED IN SPAIN.	45

List of Figures

FIGURE 1. SCHEMATIC ILLUSTRATION OF INTERACTIVE CO-DEVELOPMENT AND CO-EVALUATION PROCESS.....	11
FIGURE 2. SCREENSHOT OF DIANA PLATFORM VIEWER FOR MANCHA-ORIENTAL PILOT AREA.	18
FIGURE 3. "POLYGON TOOL" IMPLEMENTED IN THE BETA VERSION OF THE PLATFORM.	23
FIGURE 4. TRAFFIC LIGHT EXAMPLE OF SANNIO ALIFANO WHERE RED ARE AREAS ARE IRRIGATED PARCELS WITHOUT NECESSARY WATER RIGHTS. YELLOW CORRESPONDS TO IRRIGATED AREAS EXCEEDING THE DECLARED IRRIGATED AREAS GREEN ARE AREAS WITH NECESSARY WATER RIGHTS THAT ARE SIMILAR TO THE DECLARED IRRIGATED AREAS.....	38
FIGURE 5. LIST OF ASSISTANTS TO THE MEETING ORGANIZED IN ITALY.	44
FIGURE 6. LIST OF ASSISTANTS IN ROMANIAN MEETING.....	47

Executive summary

Participatory evaluation of the new DIANA services jointly with users and other stakeholders is the core element of the project. The campaigns are a basic piece in this evaluation. First, they are the mechanism to provide the required datasets (field measurements, EO data, additional data, stakeholder data and perceptions) that are needed to generate DIANA portfolio products for stakeholder test group. Second, they provide the frame of reference for the stakeholder co-evaluation process.

The purpose of this document is to describe the activities in the process of co-evaluation and validation of the DIANA platform, which have been centred around the alpha- and beta-version of the platform viewer and comprehensive dataset of the 2017-2019 growing seasons in all pilots.

In the technical report of 2nd year, eight steps were described to develop the pilot deployment and co-evaluation process. But during the 3rd year, these steps have been updated resulting in nine steps described below:

- Step 1. A common set of definitions of products for upload and display has been elaborated in order to ensure consistency between all pilots.
- Step 2. Complete datasets of these products for 2017 growing season were prepared offline using a combination of pre-alpha platforms (SPIDERwebGIS, MOSES/Minaret, Irrisat) and standard GIS software. For 2018 and 2019 all the products have been uploaded and are available into DIANA platform.
- Step 3. Uploading these products to the platform via an FTP bridge. Now, in all the pilots, these products are available both as annual and monthly data.
- Step 4. Elaboration of the User's Guide of the DIANA platform viewer in an iterative way. The "DIANA User's Guide" (D4.2) is a well-tailored tutorial, consisting of ready to use training material on how to utilize the platform and exploit the information services provided. During the third year the DIANA users guide has been updated including the new functionalities implemented thanks to the user's opinions and feedback. A video tutorial has been made to facilitate the use of the platform by users. (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5duocejr9JY>).
- Step 5. The technical teams provided training of platform viewer to users, both in person and via skype. These training meetings were found to be more effective than webinars. In addition, several meetings between the partners with further target groups were carried out during the second and third year (see WP6) to explain the services provided by DIANA platform and how it can be useful for their work in the future.
- Step 6. As soon as pilot campaign data products were available for viewing on the DIANA platform, the Core Users have started to evaluate the performance, usefulness and benefits of DIANA tools, as compared to their routine operations and decision-making. This part of the evaluation has been supported by members of pilot area teams. It was continued in the third year. Feedback has been collected from Core Users through questionnaires, interviews and meetings.

- Step 7. Along the same lines and in parallel, the technical aspects of the platform have been evaluated mainly by AgriSat and Ariespace technicians, who are experts in the use of EO agriculture platforms. They have been continuously working hand-in-hand with DIANA platform developers AgroApps, helping to improve the technical aspects of the platform, such as appearance, accessibility, usability, functionality, and adaptability.
- Step 8. The technical and user feedback has led to iterations with the platform developer team and have been the basis for the (beta) version of the platform totally operational. Figure 1 illustrates this interaction.
- Step 9. During the third year, regional meetings have taken place. Authorities from pilot river basins, ministries and water user association attended these meetings providing their opinions and evaluation for validation of DIANA beta-platform and services. This information has been very useful also to provide indications about how much they are willing to introduce DIANA services in their routine tasks beyond the project.

In conclusion, the beta version of the platform has been updated successfully incorporating the tools and ideas proposed by the technicians and users reflected in interviews, questionnaires, meetings, etc... The products have been validated and recognized as a high-value product at different user's levels. The interest raised has led to more water user associations joining the co-evaluation process. In particular, the Spanish Ministry of Ecological Transition, in collaboration with the Ministry of Agriculture, has started to play an even more active role in implementing and co-evaluating DIANA services in more river basins, generating within the pilot areas specialized positions to work specifically on these subjects.

In Spain, the brand "Hidrogestor" has been created and registered in order to respond to the incipient demand from users.

In Italy, the brand "Irrisat" has been updated for this purpose.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and scope of the document

Participatory evaluation of the new DIANA services jointly with users and other stakeholders is the core element of the project. The corresponding activities are assembled in Work package 4 (WP4), which is closely interrelated with WP1 (co-creation). The principal objective is here to evaluate in a participatory process the use and performance of the three DIANA services (irrigation water abstractions, drought monitoring and drought forecast, and support to the implementation of the Water Framework Directive) in our pilot Case Studies (Spain, Italy, Romania).

The campaigns are an essential piece in this evaluation. First, they are the mechanism to provide the required datasets (field measurements, EO data, additional data, stakeholder data and perceptions) that are needed to generate DIANA portfolio products for stakeholder test groups (Task 4.2). Second, they provide the frame of reference for the stakeholder co-evaluation process (Task 4.3).

The core philosophy of DIANA is to make the project a joint venture of stakeholders and the project team. The objective is to establish a sense or fact of co-ownership, which is an indispensable condition for true empowerment of stakeholders for sustainable implementation (i.e., continuity of DIANA services beyond the project end) of any tool or measure.

Therefore, users and other stakeholders in all pilot areas have been consulted from the very beginning of the project, embedded in a process of co-creating the DIANA products, tools, and services together with users and other stakeholders. The conversations and feedback have been maintained continuously from the beginning to the end of the project.

The purpose of this document is to describe the status of the second and third step in the pilot deployment and co-evaluation, Tasks 4.2 and 4.3, which are dedicated to *“Deployment of the pilots”* and *“Pilot co-evaluation and co-validation”*.

It provides a brief summary of the basic pilot deployment and co-evaluation concepts, followed by details of the pilot campaign implementation and execution in the pilot areas and the subsequent phase of verification and participatory evaluation with users.

The first step in the pilot deployment and co-evaluation process was described in D4.1 (DIANA pilot deployment, monitoring, and co-evaluation plan). The companion document D4.2 (User guide and training material) has supported the pilot deployment and co-evaluation process, D4.3 described the strategies followed up to the second year of the project in order to make a constant co-evaluation and co-validation hand to hand with the users, collecting feedback provided and summarizing the conclusions extracted. The current document D4.4 is an actualisation of the D4.3 in order to describe the process and the conclusions of the third year of the project.

1.2. Context of DIANA users and services

Much of the work in DIANA is based on the comprehensive work carried out in precursor projects (e.g., SIRIUS¹, ERMOT², Irrisat³) and in particular the Copernicus study “Applying Earth observation to support the detection of non-authorized water abstractions” (DG-ENV 2014).

Users and other stakeholders in all pilot areas have been consulted from the very beginning of the project. This builds on long-standing collaboration during past and ongoing projects of the local partners. In all pilot areas, some stakeholders are already familiar with EO-assisted information products, since all technical partners have a long and outstanding tradition in the development of EO methodology and its practical use in agricultural and water-related applications.

In order to accelerate and dynamize the co-creation process, activities of WP4 (pilot deployment, see D4.1) have been started in parallel with the co-creation process (WP1).

In each pilot area, an existing pre-alpha version of the platform (see Task 1.3) was implemented during the first project months, with level-0 DIANA information products provided to the core users during one irrigation season. Consequently, the co-creation discussions were focused around concrete cases of direct relevance to the core users (displaying their own data).

In accordance with the specific nature of DIANA users (public authorities in many cases), the co-creation activities were focused on a small group or one-to-one meetings with the core users. The users were shown the available information products (maps of irrigated areas, maps of irrigation and crop water requirements, colour composite maps) on the existing platforms (SPIDER, Irrisat, Minaret) during these meetings and also got access to these platforms (some of them have already had access for a significant period of time), so they could evaluate for themselves the usefulness and suitability for their routine tasks and give input to the service and platform development. This was important due to the fact the users had very vivid idea of the products to work in from the very beginning of the project and they could start to define their requirements and evaluate the usefulness very soon what gives us a lot time to improve and adjust all the DIANA services to the users.

1.3. The nine steps of pilot deployment and co-evaluation

This section summarises the steps needed in the pilot deployment and co-evaluation process. It serves as a document structure and provides a preview of outcomes. The details of procedures and results are given in the corresponding section in the rest of the document [Steps 1-3 in section 2.3 (pilot deployment), steps 4-9 in section 3].

¹ www.sirius-gmes.es

² <http://maps.spiderwebgis.org/login/?custom=ermot>

³ www.irrisat.it

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

- Step 1. A common set of definitions of products for upload and display has been elaborated in order to ensure consistency between all pilots.
- Step 2. Complete datasets of these products for 2017 growing season were prepared offline using a combination of pre-alpha platforms (SPIDERwebGIS, MOSES/Minaret, Irrisat) and standard GIS software. For 2018 and 2019 all the products have been uploaded and are available into DIANA platform.
- Step 3. Upload of these products to the platform via an FTP bridge. Now, in all the pilots, these products are available both as annual and monthly data.
- Step 4. Elaboration of the User's Guide of the DIANA platform viewer in an iterative way (as soon as the DIANA platform viewer allowed to produce the corresponding screenshots). The "DIANA User's Guide" (D4.2) is a well-tailored tutorial, consisting of ready to use training material on how to utilise the platform and exploit the information services provided. During the third year the DIANA users guide has been updated including the new functionalities implemented thanks to the user's opinions and feedback. A video tutorial has been made to facilitate the use of the platform by users (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5duocejr9JY>).
- Step 5. The technical teams provided training of platform viewer to users, both in person and via skype. These training meetings were found to be more effective than webinars. In addition, several meetings between the partners with further target groups were carried out during the second and third year (see WP6) to explain the services provided by DIANA platform and how it can be useful for their work in the future.
- Step 6. As soon as pilot campaign data products were available for viewing on the DIANA platform, the Core Users have started to evaluate the performance, usefulness and benefits of DIANA tools, as compared to their routine operations and decision-making. This part of the evaluation has been supported by members of pilot area teams. It was continued in the third year. Feedback has been collected from Core Users through questionnaires, interviews and meetings.
- Step 7. Along the same lines and in parallel, the technical aspects of the platform have been evaluated mainly by AgriSat and Ariespace technicians, who are experts in the use of EO agriculture platforms. They have been continuously working hand-in-hand with DIANA platform developers AgroApps, helping to improve the technical aspects of the platform, such as appearance, accessibility, usability, functionality, and adaptability.
- Step 8. The technical and user feedback has led to iterations with the platform developer team and have been the basis for the (beta) version of the platform totally operational. Figure 1 illustrates this interaction.
- Step 9. During the third year, 7 regional meetings have been taken place. Authorities from pilot river basins, ministries and water user association attended these meetings providing their opinions and evaluation for validation of DIANA beta-platform and services. This information has been very useful also provide indications about how much they are willing to introduce DIANA services in their routine tasks beyond the project.

Working together among developers, users, ...

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of interactive co-development and co-evaluation process.

2. The DIANA pilot deployment and campaign execution

As explained in D4.1, the deployment of DIANA tools and services is effected in three phases, each covering one growing season (or hydrological year, depending on each user's internal functioning), roughly coinciding with one project year. These are:

Phase 1 - Pre-campaign (2017): Deployment of pre-alpha version of DIANA platform during co-creation process with Core Users.

Phase 2 - Pilot campaign (2018): Deployment of alpha version, co-creation continuing, evaluation with Core Users ("alpha users") starting.

Phase 3 - Validation campaign (2019): Deployment of beta version, evaluation with alpha- and beta users.

2.1. The concept of pilot deployment, campaigns and Core Users

Participatory evaluation of the new DIANA services jointly with users and other stakeholders is the core element of the project. The principal objective is here to evaluate in a participatory process the use and performance of the DIANA services in our pilot Case Studies (Spain, Italy, Romania).

The campaigns are a basic piece in this evaluation. First, they are the mechanism to provide the required datasets (field measurements, EO data, additional data, stakeholder data and perceptions) that are needed to generate DIANA portfolio products for stakeholder test groups (Task 4.2). Second, they provide the frame of reference for the stakeholder evaluation process (Task 4.3).

In the three DIANA pilot area countries Spain (ES), Italy (IT), and Romania (RO), DIANA Core Users are listed in Table 1 (from D1.2). In the case of Spain, the objective has been to assemble all Core User levels, in order to explore and demonstrate possible ways of scaling the DIANA services to the national level.

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

Table 1. DIANA Core Users (from D1.2).

	Name	Identification	Involved in Copernicus study	Consortium partner or liaison partner
ES	Bembézar Margen Derecha	Irrigation scheme WUA*	N	FERAGUA
ES	Junta Central de Regantes La Mancha Oriental	Aquifer WUA	Y	AgriSat
IT	Consorzio di Bonifica del Sannio Alifano	Irrigation scheme WUA	Y	Sannio Alifano
RO	S.C. Emiliana West (Banat)	Irrigation scheme WUA	N	NARW
ES	MAPAMA (Ministry of Agriculture)	National government	Y	AgriSat
ES	Tierra del Vino (Duero)	Irrigation scheme WUA/ river-basin authority	Y	AgriSat / MAPAMA
ES	Bajo Jalón (Ebro)	Irrigation scheme WUA/ river-basin authority	Y	AgriSat / MAPAMA

*WUA = Water Users Association

The pilot areas have been selected according to the most promising precursor applications and implementation conditions on one hand and on the other hand for having contributed to the Copernicus study.

The implementation has been carried out by the partners in charge of technology development: FERAGUA (assisted by CSIC Institute of Sustainable Agriculture) in Bembézar Margen Derecho, AgriSat (assisted by subcontractor University of Castilla-La Mancha, the original developer of SPIDERwebGIS®) in the remaining Spanish pilots, ROSA (in collaboration with AgriSat and UCLM) in Romania, and Ariespace in Sannio Alifano. A corresponding methodology harmonization and training workshop was held in Albacete in July 2017 with all pilot areas present.

The campaigns have been conceived in a flexible way, in order to adapt to the specific character of each pilot area. Depending on each pilot area, the technical campaigns will be conducted for different purposes and under different configurations and the stakeholder component will be tuned to the water-related problems or conflicts in the area.

The central DIANA Integrated Water Abstractions Service (DIWAS) has been implemented and evaluated in all pilots during the second project year. It has become available after the summer. Therefore, the growing season for evaluation was selected as 2017, where a complete dataset is available. Once the year 2017 was evaluated it turned into the operational campaign jointly with 2018. 2019 data set have been established as real operational phase taking into account the user's requirement needs providing the products at the correct timing and translating the regular year (from January to December) to the hydrological year (from October to September) for some of the pilots (Bembézar and Mancha Oriental) as they required.

All pilot areas are also serving to test and further develop other services. The Júcar river-basin in Spain is one of the EU Water Framework Directive pilot areas. The Spanish national ministry has been actively collaborating in developing and testing the WFD implementation support service.

The Sannio Alifano irrigation scheme in Italy has been supported by our Italian partners (again users and EO experts at the same time) for several years, with university spin-off company Ariespace providing commercial services and the Regional ministry providing the institutional support.

In Romania, partner NARW is the water agency at national level, collaborating with WUAs in different parts of the territory. Partner ROSA (national space agency) was involved in the Copernicus study and in precursor FP7 project SIRIUS.

The campaign-related tasks are split into technical issues (technical data collection and analysis, product generation and webGIS upload) and non-technical issues (framework, training, stakeholder process and evaluation).

2.2. Pre-campaign implementation and execution (2017)

The existing set of platforms (SPIDERwebGIS®⁴, Irrisat⁵, MOSES⁶, Minaret⁷) have been serving as the pre-alpha version of the DIANA platform on one hand. They will continue forming part of the final DIANA platform configuration (available for more detailed requests of expert users) on the other hand (see D1.3).

The pre-campaign has been focused on the main DIANA service (water abstractions). According to the responses of all Core Users to the set of questionnaires distributed to them and discussed with them (see D1.1), their initial (“level 1”) requirements of information products for water abstractions monitoring are summarised in Table 2 (from D1.1). These products were generated and uploaded on the existing platforms and discussed with the Core Users in each pilot.

⁴ www.SPIDERwebGIS.org

⁵ www.irrisat.it

⁶ moses-project.eu/moses_website

⁷ Mateos et al. (2013); González-Dugo et al. (2013)

Table 2. DIANA level 1 information products.

Information product	Periodicity
Maps of irrigated areas	Once per season
Crop inventory (map)	Annual
Maps of crop water requirements	Weekly to monthly and annual per season
Maps of crop water consumption	Idem
Maps of abstracted volumes	Once per season
Gridded water balance	Weekly to monthly and one per season

2.3. Pilot campaign implementation and execution (2018)

The pilot campaign (phase 2) was conducted in each pilot area with products provided by the technical teams (see Table 3) during one growing season with the support of the DIANA's stakeholders. The year 2017 was selected for this purpose, as it allowed the use of a comprehensive dataset in each pilot area. The pilot campaign implementation and execution entailed the first three steps of the scheme defined in section 1.3.

Table 3. Pilot areas currently included in the DIANA platform.

	Pilot area	Assisted by	Core User	Included/uploaded in DIANA platform
ES	Mancha Oriental	AgriSat /UCLM	Irrigation Users Association	✓
ES	Tierra del Vino	AgriSat /UCLM	Duero River Basin Authority	✓
ES	Bajo Jalón	AgriSat /UCLM	Ebro River Basin Authority	✓
ES	Bembézar Margen Derecha	FERAGUA	Irrigation Users Association	✓
IT	Sannio Alifano	Ariespace	Consorzio di Bonifica Sannio Alifano	✓
RO	Banat Area	AgriSat/ UCLM ROSA/ NARW	Emiliana	✓

(Step 1) A common set of definitions of products for upload and display has been elaborated in order to ensure consistency between all pilots. Box 1 summarizes the result.

Box 1. Standardized definition of basic data products for upload and display in the DIANA platform viewer.

Crop Evapotranspiration: $ET_c = Kc^* \times ET_0$, where Kc^* is the reflectance-based crop coefficient and ET_0 is the reference evapotranspiration. In Italian pilot area ET_c has been estimated based on direct calculation by the Penman Monteith equation, explicitly written in terms of albedo α , Leaf Area Index (LAI) and meteorological data (see D2.1 for more details). ET_c is the value of evapotranspiration under standard conditions, as defined by FAO56: disease-free, well-fertilized crops, under optimum soil water conditions.

Net Irrigation Water Requirement: $NWIR = ET_c - PP$, where ET_c has been defined above and PP is the effective precipitation. This product is calculated through a Soil Water Balance assisted by satellite data.

Gross irrigation water requirements: $GIWR = NIWR/\epsilon$. This product is obtained by applying an irrigation efficiency coefficient (ϵ) to the net irrigation water requirements (NIWR). In the case of La Mancha Oriental this coefficient (0.85) has been estimated for the whole pilot area in order to have an estimation of the abstracted volumes for the total of the pilot. However, it is important to keep in mind that these coefficients are very specific parameters depending mainly on the type of irrigation system and on the efficiency of the application of the water (open channels, pumping, sprinkling, dripping, irrigating climate conditions, etc).

(Step 2 and Step 3) Complete datasets of these products for 2017 growing season were prepared offline using a combination of pre-alpha platforms (SPIDERwebGIS, MOSES/Minaret, Irrisat) and standard GIS software (Table 4). For 2018 and 2019 all the products have been uploaded and are available into DIANA platform. Upload of these products to the platform via an FTP bridge. Now, in all the pilots, these products are available both as annual and monthly data. Figure 2 shows an example screenshot of the DIANA platform viewer for the La Mancha Oriental pilot area (Spain).

Table 4. Products from Pilot Areas uploaded to DIANA platform.

Pilot area partners involved		Crop Classification	Maps of Irrigated Areas	Crop Evapotranspiration (ETc)	Net Irrigation Water Requirements (NIWR)	Gross Irrigation Water Requirements (GIWR)
ES	Mancha Oriental (AgriSat/UCLM)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
ES	Tierra del Vino (AgriSat/UCLM)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
ES	Bajo Jalón (AgriSat/UCLM)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
ES	Bembézar MD (Feragua)	✓	✓	Tbd*	✓	✓
IT	Sannio Alifano (Ariespace, Sannio Alifano)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
RO	Banat Area (AgriSat/UCLM ROSA/NARW)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

* working on methodology for crops under stress

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

Figure 2. Screenshot of DIANA platform viewer for Mancha-Oriental Pilot Area.

Steps 2 and 3 have been executed by technicians from Ariespace, AgriSat and Agroapps, who dedicated important efforts to adapt pre-existing DIANA products to the technical requirements of the DIANA platform and users.

This work covered mainly:

- An adequate product format was defined, thus standardizing the characteristics needed for upload.
- The data volume of the products has been reduced. Due to the high spatial resolution (10mx10m) of the products and the large surface covered by the DIANA pilots, the data volume of products provided by the supporting groups (e.g. UCLM) is not fit for operational handling. A monthly net irrigation water requirements product e.g. is 1 GB and it has been transformed into 0.3MB. This turns any data product transfer into a cumbersome process, taking 1 hour for the net irrigation water requirement example, being 39 products per pilot area.
- Format transformations were developed in order to make DIANA products more appealing for the user.

2.4. Validation campaign implementation and execution (2019)

During the two previous campaigns the methodology to follow the product generation was established to meet the computer specifications of the DIANA platform developers and the user’s requirement needs. This process was long due to the different groups of product providers Feragua, Ariespace and AgriSat-UCLM and different requirement of the pilots. However, once the consortium had the process totally homogeneous and harmonised the 2019 it has been the most fruitfully year regarding the product generation. The 2017,2018 and, some pilots, 2019 have been generated. Table 5 summarises all the pilots and products generated and uploaded into the platform.

Table 5. Product generated per pilot area and uploaded into the platform.

		Classification	Irrigated Area	Non-Irrig. area	GIWR monthly	GIWR annual	NIWR monthly	NIWR annual	Etc monthly	Etc annual
2017	BANAT	■	■			■		■	■	■
	MANCHA ORIENTAL	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	BEMBEZAR									
	SANNIO ALIFANO	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	BAJO JALON	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	TIERRA DEL VINO	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
2018	BANAT	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	MANCHA ORIENTAL	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	BEMBEZAR	■	■	■			■	■	■	■
	SANNIO ALIFANO	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	BAJO JALON	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	TIERRA DEL VINO	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
2019	BANAT									
	MANCHA ORIENTAL	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	BEMBEZAR	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	SANNIO ALIFANO	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
	BAJO JALON									
	TIERRA DEL VINO									

For the evaluation of the platform, it was generated another table (Table 6) where all the functionalities of the platform were collected. This table was provided to the users in order to check all the functionalities are working correctly.

Other works have been developed in parallel in order to validate the products by the users. For example, for Bajo Jalón and Tierra del Vino products referred to water requirement were aggregated into the cadastral polygon scale. For crop classification products validation in Bajo Jalón user’s field-work was compared with remote sensing approach giving promising results with more than 85% of match between irrigated plots detected in field and detected by EO technicians. The final report is attached in this document as the Annex B.

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

Table 6. Table provided to the pilot areas to check all the functionalities of the platform.

			Data Boxes				Pie-Chart		Graphs				Map Vis		
			Peak demand	Irrigated area	Accumulated	Non-Irrigated	ha per crop	Ty	Volume per cr	Irrigated and	Monthly Aver	Evolution and	Average Irriga	Monthly Aver	Map Visualiz
2017	BANAT	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	MANCHA ORIENTAL	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	BEMBEZAR	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	SANNIO ALIFANO	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	BAJO JALÓN	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	TIERA DEL VINO	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
2018	BANAT	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	MANCHA ORIENTAL	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	BEMBEZAR	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	SANNIO ALIFANO	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	BAJO JALÓN	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	TIERA DEL VINO	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
2019	BANAT	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	MANCHA ORIENTAL	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	BEMBEZAR	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	SANNIO ALIFANO	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	BAJO JALÓN	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													
	TIERA DEL VINO	ETc													
		GIWR													
		NIWR													

3. The DIANA co-evaluation and validation process

At the end of the pilot campaign, the Core Users started evaluating the performance, usefulness, and benefits of DIANA tools, as compared to their routine operations and decision-making.

As described in D4.1, we distinguish three steps of the co-evaluation and validation process:

- 1) *Verification* (technical checks of conformity with specification);
- 2) *Participatory assessment with users and evaluation* (based on evaluation protocol & criteria for “fit for purpose”); this step gives indications on efficiency & “usefulness” of DIANA tools; The evaluation criteria include accuracy (“at least as good as field data”), information content (spatial resolution and coverage of large areas), reliability, economic viability, social benefits, and cultural acceptance.
- 3) *Validation* (confirmation from users that DIANA services are exactly what they want, based on a validation protocol and criteria); this step gives conclusions on effectiveness and cost-benefit, as well as further impact, it demonstrates if/that DIANA services “make a difference” for the users and their environment.

The three steps have been totally completed for all data sets of 2017 and 2018 products. However, for 2019 products are still in the process but their reliability is already set during the previous campaigns. Phases 2 and 3 have been an iterative process going back and forward until both were reached. If the assessment is good directly gives an added value to the products and the DIANA platform with a high impact in the day-to-day tasks of the users.

The process of co-evaluation and validation is being supported by and closely coordinated with the series of co-creation meetings (see WP1, Kensing and Madsen, 1991).

3.1. Verification

The technical aspects of the platform have been evaluated mainly by AgriSat and Ariespace technicians, who are experts in the use of EO agriculture platforms. They have been continuously working hand-in-hand with DIANA platform developers AgroApps, helping to improve the technical aspects of the platform, such as appearance, accessibility, usability, functionality, and adaptability. This task it has been developed from the very beginning of the platform development, monitoring simple tasks as the correct visualisation of the maps, to the very end of the project checking manually, in local computers, each functionality and data shown in the platform.

For this purpose, the main products of DIANA water abstraction service have been generated and uploaded to the beta version, the operational DIANA platform for all pilot areas (as detailed in the previous section). The procedure for products verification was following two main objectives:

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

- 1) The accuracy and reliability of the products.
- 2) The proper functioning of the DIANA platform beta version (product approach) has a correct: i) visualisation of the products; ii) statistical information derived, iii) performance of the functionalities and iv) matching with the requirements from users of different areas collected from WP1.

The products generated in DIANA, as described above (Table 4), have been provided by 3 different partners of the project, UCLM (subcontractor to AgriSat), Ariespace and Feragua.

Feragua has provided products for the Bémbezár pilot area. The University of Castilla La Mancha (UCLM) has supported four pilot areas: Bajo Jalón, Tierra del Vino, Mancha Oriental and Banat. In the case of la Mancha Oriental, Tierra del Vino, and Bajo Jalón pilots, additional efforts have been devoted to the verification of the precision, usefulness and reliability of the products. Different reports have been generated summarizing the information provided by DIANA products using GIS software by UCLM-AgriSat. Other work has been developed in parallel in order to validate the products by the users. For example, for Bajo Jalón and Tierra del Vino water requirement products were aggregated into cadastral polygon scale. For crop classification products validation in Bajo Jalón user's field-work was contrasted against remote sensing approach giving promising results with more than 85% of match between irrigated plots detected in field and detected by EO technicians. The final report is attached in this document as the Annex B.

For the Romanian pilot area of Banat, AgriSat technicians, supported by UCLM, have generated the 2017 DIANA products, always in close collaboration with ROSA and NARW (process described in the previous deliverable D4.3). For the generation of 2018 Romanian products, ROSA technicians went to Albacete where AgriSat and UCLM are located in order to collaborate in the product generation with the tools developed by UCLM and with the help of AgriSat technicians. 2018 Banat product generation procedure was implemented as follows:

- 1.- ROSA provided the crop classification maps to AgriSat.
- 2.- A member from ROSA team travelled to Albacete and jointly the AgriSat-UCLM team work together in order to give the tips and teach the process of the generation of the products. The software use was explained giving the tools for Romania team to finish the work for 2018 product generation.
- 3.- ROSA member finish the generation of the data set of 2018 Banat products.
- 4.-Products were uploaded to the platform.

Ariespace has provided the products related to Sannio Alifano. In order to quantify the accuracy of the methodological approach in the Italian pilot, a comparison of the water volume applied and GIWR estimated from EO data was performed considering a sample of farms. The information was provided by the Consorzio di Bonifica Sannio Alifano, in terms of cadastral coordinates (municipality, sheet and parcel) and identity of land-owners. In this phase, considering also the classification results, it was possible to compare the irrigated area declared by the farmers and those estimated from EO data (more details can be found in D2.3).

After a pre-processing of the information to adapt the products to the requirements of the DIANA platform developers, all the products have been uploaded and have been verified by their corresponding pilot area teams.

Each pilot has verified the 2017 and 2018 products and statistics shown in DIANA platform are correct. Currently, the 2019 products are being checked by the users.

During the last period of the beta platform development the “polygon tool” has been implemented. This tool allows the user to run statistics for specific areas of interest in an online way (Figure 3). The requirement of this functionality was made by the users and it means a huge step for DIANA platform making it more dynamic and innovative. The technical team of AgriSat has followed the development of this tool very near checking manually the results provided by the platform and making sure they were correct. The monitoring process has been intense in time and has implied technical changes in the basic DIANA products format requirements. Many teleconference and meetings between the two groups AgriSat and Agroapps have had place in order to develop correctly this tool.

The procedure has been as following:

- The user can define the area of interest in two ways:
 - o By uploading an existing polygon
 - o By drawing a polygon by himself in the platform

Figure 3. "Polygon tool" implemented in the beta version of the platform.

3.2. Participatory service evaluation and validation

This section reports on steps 4-6 of the scheme defined in section 1.3.

(Step 4) The User's Guide of the DIANA platform viewer has been released in an iterative way (as soon as the DIANA platform viewer allowed to produce the corresponding screenshots). The "DIANA User's Guide" (D4.2) is a well-tailored tutorial, consisting of ready to use training material

on how to use the platform viewer and explore the information services provided. The updated document DIANA User's Guide has been generated with the beta version of the platform and a video tutorial was made to show how the platform works as an easy way for the users.

(Step 5) The technical teams provided training of the platform viewer to users, both in-person and via skype. These training meetings were found to be more effective than webinars. In addition, several meetings between the partners and with further target groups were carried out during the second year (see WP6) to explain the services provided by DIANA platform and how it can be useful for their work in the future.

(Step 6) As soon as pilot campaign data products were available for viewing on the DIANA platform, the Core Users have started to evaluate the performance, usefulness and benefits of DIANA tools, as compared to their routine operations and decision-making. This part of the evaluation has been supported by members of pilot area teams. It will continue in the third year. Feedback has been collected from Core Users through questionnaires and interviews, as described below.

Summarizing the second period of the project, the co-evaluation was carried out following different approaches (questionnaires and in-person interviews, see deliverable D4.3) and directed to two different categories of platform viewer users:

1. From the point of view of the end-user (water manager Core Users).
2. From the point of view of technicians (beyond the technical verification described above).

During the third period the participatory assessment was approached from the point of view of regional meetings. These meetings were organized from the idea of once the users have had some experience with the products and DIANA platform during the first and second period of the project, we would like to know how they see DIANA product in an operational work routine. The meetings took place in the original countries with high authorities from different ministries and water authorities. The list of attendants is on the Annex C.

Table 7. Regional meeting organized during the 3rd year of the project in the pilot area.

Pilot Area	Date	Place	Nº assit.
Sannio Alifano	12/04/2019	Campania, Regional Agriculture Department. Centro Direzionale. Napoli. Italy	56
Tierra del Vino	01/10/2019	Head quarter of the DUERO River Basin Authority. Valladolid. Spain	4
Bajo Jalón	02/10/2019	Head quarter of the EBRO River Basin Authority. Zaragoza. Spain	6
Mancha Oriental	10/04/2019	Headquarters of Central Advisory Board of Mancha Oriental. Albacete. Spain	6
Mancha Oriental	27/11/2019	Headquarters of Central Advisory Board of Mancha Oriental. Albacete. Spain	3
Bembézar	10/09/2019	Headquarters of Bembézar water user association. Sevilla. Spain	40
Ministry Spain	21/01/2019	Ministry of Ecological Transition. Madrid. Spain	26
Banat	03/06/2019	Offices of National Administration, Romanian Waters. Bucharest. Romania	30

3.2.1. Conclusions from regional meetings with end-users

ITALY

The main idea extracted from Sannio Alifano is implementing "traffic light" alarm (Figure 4) where the Water Rights information is crossed with irrigated area products or with the DIANA crop classification layer. Some work in that direction has been developed by the Italian team working hand to hand Ariespace and Sannio Alifano Pilot area.

More in general, DIANA products/platform are considered valuable, being physically based - for instance regarding crops - and available both in time and space, moreover scalable on the territory from large areas to single cadastral parcel. So, they are essential to WUAs - and not only for them - to improve knowledge of irrigated agriculture managements itself, especially in terms of:

- Detection of irrigated areas, both with and without water rights;
- Classification of crops;
- Evaluation of irrigation water volumes used by farmers, wherever flowmeters are missing or not working. This, particularly, is possible - with satisfying accuracy - by processing on statistical basis the data obtained from cross-checks among GIWR and the corresponding measured water volumes, where they are available.

SPAIN

From Mancha Oriental the conclusions and lessons learned are:

- EO mapping of irrigated areas is a mature and operative technique, widely accepted, even by court.
- Sentinel 2 imagery offers unprecedented spatial resolution and revisit time.

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

- Users require mapping irrigated areas several times during the growing season for supporting field work. *[field work is currently needed for sanctioning an irrigated field without water rights]*
- Mediterranean permanent crops like grapes, olive, almond, among others, challenge the current EO system for differentiating irrigated and non-irrigated areas.
- EO time series of images integrated into the webGIS platform provide evidences for Irrigation Jury.
- EO mapping of Irrigation Water Requirement is giving the first steps into its operational application.
- EO-based IWR accounting requires coexisting with traditional local approaches, to which the EO must support and demonstrate the improvements achieved, such as transparency and equity, among others.
- Some easy to explain, easy to implement initiatives, such as linking irrigation water requirements to the NDVI value achieved by certain crop canopies are very relevant steps.
- Further research is needed to deal with water stress, Regulated Deficit Irrigation.
- EO services and products must be tailored to the users, farmers and water authorities.
- EO-based Crop and Irrigation Water Requirements products apply the same methodology across regions and countries.

In Bembézar, DIANA arises as to help and complement water management. DIANA has allowed continuing with the improvement of crop identification, estimation of water requirements and detection of non-authorized irrigation out of the boundaries of the district. The boom of new technologies, remote water measurements at the farm hydrants, remote information from satellites, Geographical Information Systems and an evolved agronomic knowledge acquired through experience allowed DIANA team to establish confident methodologies to improve water resources adapted to the pilot area. Future efforts should allow detection of water consumption when limited water allocation imposes crop water deficit. As a long process of adoption of these methodologies, farmers and mainly managers are now aware of new innovative tools that can complement their daily routines and have a platform where information can be visualized.

The user in pilot area Tierra del Vino is the Duero River Basin Organization (Confederación Hidrográfica del Duero, CHD). Their regulations provide two times during the year for farmers to declare the crop and surface: 1) in January is the first declaration, 2) in September is the second declaration (in case that the farmer has changed the crop during the year). In addition, a third possibility is the CAP crop declaration. So, from October to December the CHD technicians review all these declarations by means of field inspections. CHD has recognized that DIANA could help to make this procedure more efficient by guiding the field inspections directly to the fields marked as potentially non-complying and thus, saving a lot of time to the field technicians. For them it is crucial to have the water requirements and crop classification products on time, along with the possibility to upload these products to their own system. They have expressed strong interest and the intention to continue using DIANA products. Their administrative regulations would allow for paying for this information. Since DIANA started, they have created a new position in charge of EO-related tasks in the River Basin Organization.

The user in the pilot area Bajo Jalón is the Ebro River Basin Organization (Confederación Hidrográfica del Ebro, CHE). A detailed comparison of DIANA products with ground-based data from flowmeters has been performed with the collaboration of MITECO (Ministry for the Ecological Transition). The results show good agreement of the net irrigation water requirements (NIWR) products. They also indicate that the efficiency parameter in the calculation of GIWR varies across the area and thus, needs to be adjusted accordingly. The crop classification has a high accuracy index (86% for the total of the crops and 85 % for vineyard). Both the hydrological planning office and the water commissary (“Comisaría de Agua”) have currently well-functioning systems for planning and control of the whole river basin. Therefore, they are not interested in other products like DIANA in the short term. However, they do appreciate the innovation in DIANA and do not exclude changing their system in the long term. Their current system is based on cadastral information for crop and volume monitoring.

At national level in Spain, the main user is the Ministry for Ecological Transition (MITECO, until December 2018 MAPAMA) and in a second plane, also the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA). Within MITECO, the General Water Directorate (Dirección General del Agua, DGA) plays the central role. It oversees the Sub-directorate for Hydrological Planning (SGPUSA) and all River Basin Organizations. The SGPUSA is currently preparing the documentation for the closure of the 2nd planning cycle (Art. 5, WFD) and for the launch of the 3rd cycle. This means re-evaluating all agricultural (and other) uses and demands for the entire Spanish territory. In terms of agricultural use, this corresponds to the net crop water requirements as provided by DIANA. The agreement with MITECO is to continue with pilots Tierra del Vino and Bajo Jalón (which had been introduced by them at the beginning of the project) and to extend the activities to further pilots in additional river basins (Guadiana and Júcar) during the year after DIANA and define further actions from there. In this context, MITECO organized a large meeting on EO-assisted planning and monitoring of abstractions, with the presence of all peninsular RBOs.

The MAPA has always been present in DIANA meetings at MITECO. The relevant unit here is the Subdirectorate for Irrigation. It considers the DIANA products (both the maps of irrigated areas and the net water requirements) as helpful for the consolidation of its nationwide service SPIDER-SIAR, a combination of a network of 356 agrometeorological stations and EO-based classification and water balance.

ROMANIA

During the regional meeting in the Romanian pilot Emiliana West Rom, ROSA team presented the DIANA products resulted from processing the satellite imagery derived from Earth Observation, highlighting its innovative character and the fact that the use of satellite imagery in the fields of water management and agriculture is still in the pioneering phase in Romania, but they are increasingly important because of their accuracy and their potential to clarify important issues related to water management, especially water extracted for irrigation. Satellite images tend to become an important tool for field inspectors empowered to control the volumes of water used on agricultural holdings, based on these images being able to differentiate irrigated from non-irrigated plots and establishing the water requirements of different crops, as well as the actual volumes of water used for irrigation.

The Romanian pilot Emiliana West Rom is satisfied with the results from the DIANA platform and they want to continue the collaboration after the approved of the new laws for irrigation. The experts expressed their interest in extending these analyses to other cultivated lands in the country to see whether the values of the indicators presented, especially the net water requirements for irrigation, can be standardized by types of crops, taking into account, of course, that variations in these values are inherent due to all the factors that influence them. One of the key objectives of these extended analysis will be to identify the actual irrigation water consumption of each crop, both for the adaptation of agricultural practices in order to increase agricultural production and for the appropriate adjustment of the fees on the water used for on irrigation in Romania.

3.2.2. Workflow of the DIANA platform in water management

All farmers with water rights in Mancha Oriental belong to Junta Central de Regantes de la Mancha Oriental, JCRMO. Water rights are provided by Jucar River Basin always with the collaboration of JCRMO as ground true consultants.

For belonging to JCRMO farmers are required to follow the so-called “Management annual rules, coordination and control of irrigation uses” (original versions: <https://www.jcrmo.org/>).

Within this document the specifications of the next growing seasons are described adapting the criteria of the water use to the changing Jucar River Basin state, meteorological and agricultural situation year by year. For example, in 2017 they implanted a shortage of the 10% of the water right volumes to the drought situation.

In terms of water volumes control the farmers can select one of the two possibilities included in the “Document of annual rules”: “by theoretical consumptions of the crops” or “by water-meter”. DIANA has had a big importance within the first method.

If they choose “theoretical consumptions of the crops” the water volume will be estimated depending on the crop they declare. Within the “Document of annual rules” every year, there is a table were crops have an assigned volume in cubic meters per hectare. Along the next three points is described how DIANA has been introduced in the workflow of the users including the technicians of JCRMO and, consequently, all the farmers with irrigation rights in La Mancha Oriental.

a) Establishment of volumes based on NDVI thresholds:

Usually, the volumes estimated per crop type have been calculated through different methodologies established overtime. These volumes have been provided by the public Irrigation Service or Servicio de Asesoramiento de Riegos based on different approaches: actual measurements in controlled plots, field measurements and pluriannual data where tendency of the consumptions of the crops is evaluated in the last 30 years. In this way every crop has a water volume associated which represents the volume estimated to irrigate one growing cycle for that year (Table 8).

DIANA products have been implemented as a new source of information for water volumes estimation for specific crops as they are tree crops (Table 9). Before this technology was

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

implemented, the volume calculations for these tree crops were based on the shade area projected from the trees. The technicians would go farm by farm measuring manually this area directly related to the water consumption of the trees which is almost impossible in Mancha Oriental due to the big covered area. DIANA technology has become the new tool in order to discriminate different irrigation regimes among some tree crops discarding other methodologies (field measurements), making possible the control of this crops and saving time to the technical team of the water user association. JCRMO, during the regional meetings, have pointed out the good embracement of this methodology because It is objective, efficient and reproducible.

The next three tables show the tables published in the official bulletin of the region where we can see how the NDVI values have been incorporated in order to classify different crops and irrigation systems with different water requirements.

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

Table 8. Table of average consumption of irrigation water according to the management rules for the 2017 campaign*.

Anexo: Tabla de consumos medios de agua de riego de aplicación a las normas de gestión campaña 2017.

Cultivos herbáceos	Consumo (m ³ /ha)	Cultivos herbáceos	Consumo (m ³ /ha)
Adomidera	2.700	Maíz dulce	4.800
Ajo Blanco	3.000	Maíz forajero	5.700
Ajo chino	2.000	Melón, sandía, calabazas, pepino	3.200
Ajo morado	3.100	Nabiza o qelos	1.300
Alicachofa	6.750	Nabo forajero	2.000
Alfalfa (ciclo completo)	7.600	Pasto primavera apro. diente	1.000
Alfalfa riego hasta abril	750	Patata	5.800
Alfalfa riego hasta mayo	1.700	Patata temprana hasta 15 de julio	3.600
Alfalfa riego hasta junio	3.100	Pradera estacional riego de marzo a junio	2.500
Alfalfa riego hasta julio	4.900	Pradera permanente	5.000
Alfalfa riego hasta agosto	6.500	Ray-grass ciclo completo	6.800
Alfalfa con parada estival	4.200	Ray-grass con parada estival	5.250
Avena	2.300	Ray-grass (octubre-junio)	4.050
Azafrán	1.000	Ray-grass (octubre-mayo)	2.900
Bricufl, col, col de Bruselas, romanescu	3.000	Ray-grass (octubre-abril)	1.420
Camelina	1.500	Ray-grass (febrero-mayo)	1.700
Cárdeno	4.480	Remolacha	7.500
Cebada, centeno	2.450	Ricino	4.750
Cebolla	5.500	Soja	4.500
Cebolla de enero a junio	2.900	Sorgo forajero	5.600
Cebolla de septiembre a junio	3.300	Tingo	3.000
Cebolla de trasplante	4.070	Tricalce grano	3.150
Cereal de invierno como foraje	1.600	Veza foraje	2.000
Colza	2.450	Veza grano, yeros	1.500
Espinacas	2.500	Zanahoria, puerros, apio, chirivía, nabos	5.000
Gerbenzos	3.500		
Girasol	4.200		
Girasol ciclo corto 2ª cosecha	3.200	Cultivos leñosos	Consumo (m ³ /ha)
Guisante verde, guisante forajero	2.000	Olivo riego de apoyo	1.500
Guisante proteaginoso	2.200	Almendro riego de apoyo	1.800
Habas, habonillos	2.000	Almendro y olivo riego intensivo	3.000
Hortícolas ciclo corto	2.500	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera 1 año	1.500
Hortícolas de verano (tomate, pimiento) y hortalizas	5.500	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera 2 años	2.000
Judía verde	2.300	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera 3 años	2.500
Judía seca	3.300	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera adulta	3.000
Lechuga 3 ciclos	7.500	Encinas buñeros, pinos	1.000
Lechuga 2 ciclos	5.000	Frutales 1 año	1.500
Lechuga 1 ciclo	2.500	Frutales 2 años	2.000
Lenteja	1.500	Frutales 3 años	2.500
Lino	2.800	Frutales adultos	2.800
Maíz 300	6.050	Nogal 1 año	1.500
Maíz 400	6.150	Nogal 2 años	2.000
Maíz 500	6.250	Nogal 3 años	2.550
Maíz 600	6.350	Nogal 4 años	3.100
Maíz 700	6.450	Nogal adulto	3.800
Maíz de multiplicación	5.300	Pistachos	1.500
		Vid	1.500

(* https://www.jcrmo.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/2017NORMAS_GESTION_PLAN_EXPLORACION_2017_aprobadas.pdf)

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

Table 9. Table of average consumption of irrigation water according to the management rules for the 2018 campaign*.

Tabla de las normas 2018			
Cultivos herbáceos	Consumo (m3/ha)	Cultivos herbáceos	Consumo (m3/ha)
Adornidera	2.700	Maíz dulce	4.800
Ajo Blanco	3.000	Maíz forrajero	5.700
Ajo chino	2.000	Melón, sandía, calabazas, pepino	3.200
Ajo morado	3.100	Nabiza o grelos	1.300
Alcachofa	7.000	Nabo forrajero	2.000
Alfalfa (ciclo completo)	7.800	Pasto primavera aprov. diente	1.000
Alfalfa riego hasta abril	750	Patata	5.500
Alfalfa riego hasta mayo	1.700	Patata temprana hasta 15 de julio	4.000
Alfalfa riego hasta junio	3.200	Pradera estacional riego de marzo a junio	2.500
Alfalfa riego hasta julio	5.000	Pradera permanente	5.000
Alfalfa riego hasta agosto	6.500	Ray-grass ciclo completo	7.000
Alfalfa con parada estival	4.200	Ray-grass con parada estival	5.500
Avena	2.300	Ray-grass (octubre-junio)	4.200
Azafrán	1.000	Ray-grass (octubre-mayo)	2.900
Brócoli, col, col de Bruselas, romanescu	3.000	Ray-grass (octubre-abril)	1.420
Camelina	1.500	Ray-grass (febrero-mayo)	2.000
Cártamo	4.480	Remolacha	7.500
Cebada, centeno	2.450	Ricino	6.000
Cebolla	5.800	Soja	4.500
Cebolla de enero a junio	2.900	Sorgo forrajero	5.600
Cebolla de septiembre a junio	3.300	Trigo	3.000
Cebolla de trasplante	4.070	Triticale grano	3.150
Cereal de invierno como forraje	1.600	Veza forraje	2.000
Colza	2.450	Veza grano, yeros	1.800
Espinacas	2.500	Zanahoria, puerros, apio, chirivía, nabos	5.000
Garbanzos	3.500	Cultivos leñosos	Consumo (m3/ha)
Girasol	4.200	Almendro riego de apoyo	1.500
Girasol ciclo corto 2ª cosecha	3.400	Almendro, pistacho y olivo riego intensivo (NDVI $\geq 0.35 < 0.45$)	3.000
Guisante verde, guisante forrajero	2.000	Almendro, pistacho y olivo riego superintensivo (NDVI ≥ 0.45)	4.000
Guisante proteaginoso	2.200	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera 1 año	1.500
Habas, haboncillos	2.000	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera 2 años	2.000
Hortícolas ciclo corto	2.500	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera 3 años	4.000
Hortícolas de verano (tomate, pimiento) y huertas	5.500	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera adultos	6.000
Judía verde	2.300	Encinas truferas, pinos	1.000
Judía seca	3.400	Frutales 1 año	1.500
Lechuga 3 ciclos	7.500	Frutales 2 años	2.000
Lechuga 2 ciclos	5.000	Frutales 3 años	2.500
Lechuga 1 ciclo	2.500	Frutales adultos	3.500
Lenteja	1.800	Nogal 1 año	1.500
Lino	2.800	Nogal 2 años	2.000
Maíz 300	6.050	Nogal 3 años	2.550
Maíz 400	6.150	Nogal 4 años	3.100
Maíz 500	6.250	Nogal adulto	4.000
Maíz 600	6.350	Olivo riego de apoyo	1.500
Maíz 700	6.450	Pistachos riego de apoyo	1.500
Maíz de multiplicación	5.300	Vid	1.500

(* https://www.icrmo.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/2018NORMAS_GESTION_PLAN_EXPLORACION_2018_DEFINITIVO.pdf)

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

Table 10. Table of average consumption of irrigation water according to the management rules for the 2019 campaign*.

Anexo: Tabla de consumos medios de agua de riego de aplicación a las normas de gestión campaña 2019.

Cultivos herbáceos	Consumo (m ³ /ha)	Cultivos herbáceos	Consumo (m ³ /ha)
Adornidera	2.700	Maiz dulce	4.800
Ajo Blanco	3.000	Maiz forajero	5.700
Ajo chino	2.200	Melón, sandía, calabazas, pepino	3.200
Ajo morado	3.100	Nabiza o grelos	1.300
Alcachofa	7.000	Nabo forajero	2.000
Alfalfa (ciclo completo)	7.800	Pasto primavera aproxi. diente	1.000
Alfalfa riego hasta abril	750	Patata	5.500
Alfalfa riego hasta mayo	1.700	Patata temprana hasta 15 de julio	4.000
Alfalfa riego hasta junio	3.200	Pradera estacional riego de marzo a junio	2.500
Alfalfa riego hasta julio	5.000	Pradera permanente	5.000
Alfalfa riego hasta agosto	6.500	Ray-grass ciclo completo	7.000
Alfalfa con parada estival	4.200	Ray-grass con parada estival	5.500
Avena	2.300	Ray-grass (octubre-junio)	4.400
Azafrán	1.000	Ray-grass (octubre-mayo)	3.100
Brócoli, col, col de Bruselas, romanesco	3.000	Ray-grass (octubre-abril)	1.600
Camelina	1.500	Ray-grass (febrero-mayo)	2.000
Cardano	4.480	Remolacha	7.500
Cebada, centeno	2.450	Ricino	6.000
Cebolla	5.800	Soja	4.500
Cebolla de enero a junio	2.900	Sorgo forajero	5.600
Cebolla de septiembre a junio	3.300	Tiño	3.000
Cebolla de trasplante	4.070	Triticale grano	3.150
Cereal de invierno como forraje	1.600	Veza foraje	2.000
Colza	2.600	Veza grano, yeros	1.800
Espinacas	2.500	Zanahoria, puerros, apio, chívia, nabos	5.000
Gerbenos	3.500	Cultivos leñosos	Consumo (m ³ /ha)
Girasol	4.200	Almendro riego de apoyo	1.800
Girasol ciclo corto 2ª cosecha	3.400	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera 1 año	1.500
Guisante verde, guisante forajero	2.000	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera 2 años	2.000
Guisante proteaginoso	2.200	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera 3 años	4.000
Habas, habonillos	2.000	Chopos, paulonia y otros para madera adultos	6.000
Hortícolas ciclo corto	2.500	Encinas buferas, pinos	1.000
Hortícolas de verano (tomate, pimiento) y huertas	5.500	Frutales 1 año	(1.500)
Judía verde	2.300	Frutales 2 años	2.000
Judía seca	3.400	Frutales 3 años	2.500
Lechuga 3 ciclos	7.500	Frutales adultos	3.500
Lechuga 2 ciclos	5.000	Frutos secos, olivo y otros riego (0.35≤NDVI<0.45)	3.000
Lechuga 1 ciclo	2.500	Frutos secos, olivo y otros riego intensivo (0.45≤NDVI<0.55)	4.000
Lenteja	1.800	Frutos secos, olivo y otros riego superintensivo (NDVI ≥0.55)	5.000
Lino	2.800	Nogal 1 año	1.500
Maiz 300	6.050	Nogal 2 años	2.000
Maiz 400	6.150	Nogal 3 años	2.550
Maiz 500	6.250	Nogal 4 años	3.100
Maiz 600	6.350	Nogal adulto	4.000
Maiz 700	6.450	Olivos pistacho riego de apoyo	1.500
Maiz de multiplicación	5.300	Vid	1.500

(* https://www.jcrmo.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/NORMAS_GESTI%C3%93N_PLAN_EXPLORACI%C3%93N_2019.pdf)

In the three tables we see for the three years of DIANA (2017,2018,2019) how NDVI thresholds have been incorporating from 2017, where there is no NDVI discrimination, 2018 where we have two categories and 2019 where we have three ranges. In the forthcoming years is thought to keep working in this direction creating more groups. From this approach we consider a huge step seeing DIANA technology in this very operational level and jumped into the day to day regular tasks of the users of La Mancha Oriental.

b) Direct identification of the irrigation management

At the beginning of the year, farmer declares the crops they are intended to grow and, in needed cases, the irrigation management. In the case of irrigated olives and nut trees (mainly almond and

pistachio) the farmer the irrigation system declaration is very easy to check thanks to DIANA technology because they can be discriminated by satellite images. This fact makes possible for JCRMO technical team to go forward for future consumptions and forecasting illegal abstractions before the abstraction is made. JCRMO technicians have been very clear, on their objective: they don't want to catch non-compliant users, they want to forecast an illegality and step forward it in order to reverse the situation before occurring, and DIANA facilitates this goal. This methodology has been embraced and implemented very easy due to their transparency, objectivity among others, efficiency and reproducible.

c) Facilitating monitoring the irrigated surface and volumes control.

One of the most important tasks is JCRMO is monitoring the compliance of farmer's declaration at the beginning of the growing season with the reality. They declare:

- The crops are planned to grow.
- Number of hectares of each crop.
- Where are located.

This task starts as soon as the farmer declares and finishes at the end of the hydrological year (October) which means the technicians are the whole year constantly checking farmers declarations.

Crop classification DIANA service facilitates this task following the next steps:

- Quick comparison between DIANA crop classification and farmer's declaration layer in a computer at JCRMO office. This implies irrigated surface and volumes derived from the type and hectares of each crop.
- Field inspection: the technician goes to the non-compliance areas and confirm or not the irregularity. Without DIANA services this task would be randomly inspections.
- The farmer is warned about what the technician reported is some illegality is found.
- The situation is reversed if it is possible. If not, the case goes to an intern irrigation jury in order to evaluate the situation. DIANA services provide proofs for sanctioning.

By these meaning DIANA service have been evaluated by JCRMO as a management tool for the balance of the aquifer and very useful in order to improve the so called "Management annual rules, coordination and control of irrigation uses".

In Tierra del Vino (Duero) they have two times for farmers to declare the crop and surface: 1) in January is the first declaration, 2) in September is the second declaration (in case that the farmer has changed the crop during the year), 3) other possibility is de CAP crop declarations. So, from October to December they review all these declarations. With the introduction of DIANA products into the work chain the process will be: upload DIANA products into their system and compare spatially and numerically the farmers declaration vs DIANA products. Not compliance between the two sources of information will be areas needed to be checked with field inspections. These tasks have been developed in a randomly way so DIANA services could help in order to guide the field inspections saving a lot of time to the field technicians and making the monitoring efforts

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

more efficient. For them having the water requirements and crop classification products on time is crucial, together with the possibility to upload the products on their own system, so they could be willing to pay for this information. Since DIANA started, they have created a role position for this EO tasks in the River Basin Body.

4. Conclusions

The objective and purpose achieved during the campaigns carried out in the framework of WP4 until the last period of the project were:

- (1) to provide the required datasets and products generation for stakeholder pilot areas;
- (2) to provide the frame of reference with alpha and beta version of DIANA platform to show the products and graphics derived from the products representing interest information, training, and guidance for the stakeholder evaluation process.
- (3) feedback and evaluation of the products and platform.

In conclusion, during the third year the beta version of the platform has been updated successfully incorporating the tools and ideas proposed by the technicians and users reflected in interviews, questionnaires, meetings, etc... The products have been validated and recognised as a high-value product at different user's levels. The interest raised has led to more water user associations joining the co-evaluation process. In particular, the Spanish Ministry of Ecological Transition, in collaboration with the Ministry of Agriculture, has started to play an even more active role in implementing and co-evaluating DIANA services in more river basins, generating within the pilot areas specialised positions to work specifically on these subjects.

In Spain, the brand "Hidrogestor" has been created and registered in order to respond to the incipient demand from users.

In Italy, the brand "Irrisat" has been updated for this purpose.

References

- Antunes, P., Karadzic, V., Santos, R., Beça, P., Osann, A., 2011. Participatory multi-criteria analysis of irrigation management alternatives: The case of Caia irrigation district, Portugal. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 9, 2, 334-349.
- González-Dugo, M.P., Escuin, S., Cano, F., Cifuentes, V., Padilla, F.L.M., Tirado, J.L., Oyonarte, N., Fernández, P., Mateos, L. 2013. Monitoring evapotranspiration of irrigated crops using crop coefficients derived from time series of satellite images. II. Application on basin scale. *Agricultural Water Management*. 125:92-104.
- Kensing, F. and K. Madsen, 1991: *Generating Visions: Future Workshops and Metaphorical Design*. In *Design at Work*. Edited by Greenbaum and Kyng. Hillsdale, Lawrence Elbaum Associates Inc. Publishers,155-168.
- Mateos, L., González-Dugo, M.P., Testi, L., Villalobos, F.J. 2013. Monitoring evapotranspiration of irrigated crops using crop coefficients derived from time series of satellite images. I. Method validation. *Agricultural Water Management*. 125:81-91

Annexes

Annex A. Summarize of co-evaluation process in D4.3

In this annex a summarize of co-evaluation process carried out during the second year is showed.

Table 11. Participants in the 1st round of questionnaires about the DIANA platform.

ID	Country	Pilot Area	Organization
ID1	Italy	Sannio Alifano	ARIESPACE s.r.l.
ID2	Italy	Sannio Alifano	ARIESPACE s.r.l.
ID3	Italy	Sannio Alifano	Consorzio di Bonifica Sannio Alifano
ID4	Italy	Sannio Alifano	ARIESPACE s.r.l.
ID5	Italy	Sannio Alifano	ARIESPACE s.r.l.
ID6	Spain	Mancha Orienta	Junta Central de Regantes Mancha Oriental
ID7	Romania	Banat	NARW/ Banat Water Basin Administration
ID8	Spain	Bembézar MD	Feragua

Conclusions from co-evaluation meetings with end-users

Table 12. Ideas from the first steps in the co-evaluation and the status of the improvements.

	Pilot area	Conclusions	Status
ES	Mancha Oriental	DIANA products/platform as provided can save time for the technicians in charge of field inspections.	Implemented
		DIANA products/platform help them to have more information about the real volumes of consumption and can help to establish the volumes per crop in the year.	Implemented
		Integrate the function of spatial and temporal analysis is considered a high added value to the platform.	Ongoing
ES	Bembézar	Stresses the requirement to detect over-irrigation during the years of restrictions.	Ongoing
ES	Tierra del Vino	Points out the need to create the products referred to the cadastral polygon layer.	Implemented

ES	Bajo Jalón, Mancha	Practical application of DIANA services for detecting conflicting areas and for establishing volumes per crop type.	Implemented
IT	Sannio Alifano	DIANA can help WUA and other organizations to detect irrigated areas, both with or without water rights, classification of crops and evaluation of water irrigation volumes used by farmers. See also "Traffic light" alarm described above.	Ongoing
RO	Banat Area	Pilot area has stressed the need for using radar satellite data in order to detect humidity in the surface of the fields.	Ongoing

EO to detect water rights status

Figure 4. Traffic light example of Sannio Alifano where RED are areas are irrigated parcels without necessary water rights. YELLOW corresponds to irrigated areas exceeding the declared irrigated areas GREEN are areas with necessary water rights that are similar to the declared irrigated areas.

Conclusions from co-evaluation meetings with technicians

Specifically, the main suggested improvements extracted from different meetings among technicians are:

Table 13. Summary of the opinions about the platform functionalities.

DIANA Platform Functionalities			
	Very Good	Good	Poor
Manageable	3	5	
Intuitive	4	4	
Visualization	5	3	

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

Layers Terminology	4	3	1	
Understanding results	3	5		
Advantages of the platform	Very Useful 3	Useful 4	I don't know 1	
How often do you use it	Daily 1	Weekly 5	Once a month 1	2-3 times a year 1
User's Guide	Very Useful 1	Useful 7		
Comments				
ID7. The User Guide looks fine, I think what it contains now should get the job done.				
ID8. Spanish language will be appreciated.				
ID8. More technical information of DIANA's products in the user's guide.				

Table 14. Water Abstraction Service evaluation by the users.

Water Abstractions		
	Yes	No
Give you all the information that you need	6	2
Presentation of the information helpful	7	1
Data in graphics well understood	8	-
Maps well understood	8	-
Comments		
ID8. In its present state, the platform does not meet the expectation of detecting irrigation over abstractions in years of limited allocation. We think we still will need to read the water counters frequently.		
ID8. I'd like to see expected values and over abstractions.		
ID8. Need to find a description of the indexes and how to relate them with drought.		

In the case of the Drought Monitoring Service, the users are missing more information about the products provided by the platform to check if they can incorporate them into their work (Table 15 **Error! Reference source not found.**).

Table 15. Drought Monitoring Service evaluation by the users.

Drought Monitoring		
	Yes	No
Give you useful information	6	1
Maps well understood	6	2
Comments		
ID8. Need to find a description of the indexes and how to relate them with drought.		

In general, the responses to the questionnaires show the same ideas and suggestions as discussed during the meetings, as described in the previous sections.

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

With these results, the next step is the feedback loop with the developers to send them the opinions and suggestions of the users, and in this way, to improve the platform globally.

Table 16. General comments and suggestions by the users.

General Comments & Suggestions
ID.3. If possible, I would prefer to use the platform for a longer time, together with Ariespace, to express more conscious opinions.
ID7.1. Map legends should have measurements units for each layer.
ID7.2. Layer transparency should be adjustable by user, because a 50% transparency, for example, will change the color compared to it being 0% transparent.
ID7.3. Is there, or is it possible, to make a download or export button, to use the layers (vector or raster format) in other GIS software for further analysis?

Annex B. Comparison of classification by EO-data (Remote Sensing) versus field information in Bajo Jalón (Spain)

A comparison between the classification by Earth-Observation data (EO) and the field information was carried out in the Bajo Jalón pilot area (Ebro River Basin Authority). In this annex the methodology and conclusions are explained.

Methodology for the comparison

It is based on a raster map with the classification by Remote Sensing carried out within the framework of the DIANA Project (RS_DIANA), and a vector map which contains the field work of the three municipalities Cariñena, Alfamen and Aguarón, with a total of 437 plots and 984 ha, which were grouped into a single *shapefile* and was provided by the Ebro River Basin Authority.

The first step has been to adjust the raster map to the vector map. In this way, the raster information has been assigned to each polygon of the vector map. Point out that almost all polygons have only one class. Only six polygons presented several classes.

Once RS_DIANA classification has been assigned to each polygon of our area of interest, it's compared with the classification obtained with the field-work, as detailed in Table 17. The comparison map together with the raster classification can be viewed on the SPIDERwebGIS platform.

Table 17. Reclassification to make the comparison between DIANA classification versus field information.

Land Use DIANA Classification Bajo Jaón (2018) (RS_DIANA)			
Class	Description	Reclassification	Description
0	Undefined	2	Rainfed
1	Spring	1	Irrigation
2	Summer	1	Irrigation
3	Pring-summer	1	Irrigation
4	Vineyard irrigated	1	Irrigation
5	Olive irrigated	1	Irrigation
6	Citrus irrigated	1	Irrigation
7	Orchards irrigated	1	Irrigation
8	Nut trees irrigated	1	Irrigation
9	Greenhouses	1	Irrigation
10	Autumn-Winter	1	Irrigation
Classification in Municipality of Aguaron, Alfamen and Cariñena (field inspection)			
Class	Description	Reclassification	Description
1	Vineyard irrigated	1	Irrigation
2	Vineyard rainfed	2	Rainfed
3	Cereal rainfed	2	Rainfed
4	Rainfed land without crop	2	Rainfed
5	Other irrigated crops	1	Irrigation
6	Abandoned land	2	Rainfed
7	Land without irrigation	2	Rainfed

Results

Table 18 shows the results obtained when comparing the classification map by Remote Sensing (RS), carried out within the framework of the DIANA project with the map in which the identification of crops has been made based on the work of field, map provided by the Ebro River Basin Authority.

Approximately half of the area compared is destined for the vineyard. By comparing the area classified by remote sensing as a vineyard with the information obtained in the field, high accuracy is obtained (Table 19).

So, the global accuracy showed in the Table 18 and Table 19 confirms that there are good agreements between the information provided by remote sensing and the field inspections.

Table 18. Comparison between DIANA classification by Remote Sensing (RS) versus field work.

Surface (all the parcels -437-)						
				FIELD		TOTAL (ha)
		Irrigated	Non irrigated			
		1	2			
RS	Irrigated	1	202,76	75,74	278,50	
	Non irrigated	2	57,12	647,95	705,07	
TOTAL (ha)			259,88	723,69	983,57	

Sample distribution 26,42 73,58 100,00

Surface (all the parcels -437-)						
				FIELD		TOTAL (ha)
		Irrigated	Non irrigated			
		1	2			
RS	Regadío	1	78,02	10,47	88,49	
	Secano	2	21,98	89,53	111,51	
TOTAL (ha)			100,00	100,00	200,00	

Global Accuracy 86,49

Table 19. Comparison for the vineyard classification (irrigated and non-irrigated) by remote sensing (RS) versus field work.

Surface (only vineyard -242-)						
				FIELD		TOTAL (ha)
		Irrigated	Non irrigated			
		1	2			
RS	Irrigated	1	193,06	38,81	231,87	
	Non irrigated	2	19,69	173,80	193,49	
TOTAL (ha)			212,75	212,61	425,36	

Sample distribution 50,02 49,98 100,00

Surface (only vineyard -242-)						
				FIELD		TOTAL (ha)
		Irrigated	Non irrigated			
		1	2			
RS	Irrigated	1	90,75	18,25	109,00	
	Non irrigated	2	9,25	81,75	91,00	
TOTAL (ha)			100,00	100,00	200,00	

Global Accuracy 86,25

Annex C. List of Assistants to Regional Meeting

In this section the lists of the meetings carried out during the year 2019 are shown.

ITALY

Figure 5. List of assistants to the meeting organized in Italy.

SPAIN

Table 20. List of assistants organized in Spain.

Meeting - 21/01/2019 - (Madrid, Spain) Ministerio de Transición Ecológica		
Nº	Assistants	Organization
1	Conchita Marcuello CMarcuello@mapama.es	MITECO
2	Tatiana Ortega tortega@mapama.es	MITECO
3	Luis Martínez Cortina	MITECO
4	Javier Ruza Rodríguez	MITECO
5	Enrique Lorezo Herrero	MITECO
6	Raquel Bravo rbravo@mapama.es	MAPA
7	Alfonso Calera alfonso.calera@uclm.es	UCLM
8	Jesús Garrido Jesus.Garrido@uclm.es	UCLM
9	Anna Osann Anna.Osann@gmail.com	AgriSat
10	María Calera Maria.calera@agrisat.es	AgriSat
11	María Llanos López mllanos.lopez@agrisat.es	AgriSat
12	Cristina Espeso Delgado ced@chduero.es	CHDuero
13	José Ángel Losada García jlosada@chebro.es	CHEbro
14	Alfonso Sancho Miró	CHGuadalquivir
15	Francisco Javier Viseas Trinidad	CHGuadiana
16	Ángel García Tena	CHGuadiana
17	Teodoro Estrela Monreal	CHJúcar
18	Laura Tanco Ballesteros	CHJúcar
19	Francisco Almagro Costa	CHSegura
20	Alberto Navas Carmena	CHTajo
21	Pedro Parias	Feragua
22	Elena Navarro Soriano	Feragua
23	Pedro Olivar	JCRMO
24	Herminio Molina	JCRMO
25	Manuel Bea Martínez	Consultant
26	Jesús García Martínez	Technician
Meeting – 10/04/2019 - (Albacete, Spain) Headquarters of Central Advisory Board of Mancha Oriental		
Nº	Assistants	Organization

D4.4 Co-evaluation and validation report (2)

1	María Calera	AgriSat
2	Anna Osann	AgriSat
3	Alfonso Calera	UCLM
4	Herminio Molina	JCRMO
5	Pedro Olivas	JCRMO
6	Francisco Gutiérrez	JCRMO
Meeting – 01/10/2019 - (Zaragoza, Spain) Headquarters of River Basin Authority of Ebro		
Nº	Assistants	Organization
1	María Calera	AgriSat
2	María-Llanos López	AgriSat
3	Miguel Ángel García Vera	CHEbro
4	José Ángel Losada	CHEbro
5	Teresa Carceller	CHEbro
6	Rogelio Galván	CHEbro
Meeting – 02/10/2019 - (Valladolid, Spain) Headquarters of River Basin Authority of Duero		
Nº	Assistants	Organization
1	María Calera	AgriSat
2	María-Llanos López	AgriSat
3	Ángel Jesús González Santos	CHDuero
4	Javier Pereira Fernández	CHDuero
Meeting - 27/11/2019 - (Albacete, Spain) Headquarters of Central Advisory Board of Mancha Oriental		
Nº	Assistants	Organization
1	Milagros Alfaro	AgriSat
2	Pedro Olivas	JCRMO
3	Juan Lozoya	JCRMO
<p><i>MITECO: Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica (Ministry of Ecological Transition)</i> <i>MAPA: Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación (Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food)</i> <i>CH: Confederación Hidrográfica (River Basin Authority)</i> <i>JCRMO: Junta Central de Regantes Mancha Oriental (of Central Advisory Board of Mancha Oriental)</i></p>		

ROMANIA

Event Report
Regional meeting

PARTICIPANTS

Name	Organization	Email	Phone number	Signature
REIEGAN MIHA	INHGA	mihai_ete@yahoo.com	0723 311 521	
BORCAN MIHAELA	INHGA	mihaela.borcan@hidro.ro	0723 40 885	
CHELSEA SILVIA	INHGA	silvia.chelcea@hidro.ro	0726 974789	
AUMITRU RALUCA	INHGA	raluca.dumitru@hidro.ro	0726 110462	
VOICU GEORGIANA	INHGA	Georgiana.voicu@hidro.ro	0736 677 657	
MORARU IRINA	INHGA	irina_moraru85@yahoo.ro	0768 65832	
RADU CATALINA	INHGA	catalina.radu@hidro.ro	0724 339 367	
RODEANU ELENA	INHGA	elena.gedeanu@hidro.ro	0755 961474	
VASILE MONICA	I.N.M.G.A	monica.vasile@hidro.ro	0769 445 539	
FLORIN LAZAR	MOBIUS	florin.lazar@mobi.us.ro	0723 352 762	
CHIVERESAN MARIA	DHI	mai@dhi.ro	0728 033 807	
BADEA ALEXANDRU	ROSA	badea@rosa.ro	0744 506 880	
MOISE CRISTIAN	ROSA	cristian.moise@rosar.ro	0723 351 390	
CALERA MARIA	AGEISA	maria.calera@agnis.ro	470804828	
DEULESCU ANDREEA	ROSA	andreea.deulescu@rosar.ro	076 531 8282	
Paula Antunes	ZECO	mpa@fct.unl.pt	+351 969 09502	
STANISCIANU LAURENTIU	ANAR	laurentiu.stanisceanu@anar.ro	0768 884 074	
MIHALACHE CRISTINA	USAMVB	mihalachecristina19@gmail.com	0741 752 03	
LAZAR ANA	ROSA	ana.lazar@rosa.ro	0733 957 673	
CASAN DEAGOS	ANAR	deagos.casan@anar.ro	0723 360 571	
CROITORU RUXANDRA	ANAR	ruxandra.croitoru@anar.ro	0756 922 44	
MARICICA MONICA	ANAR	maricica.monica@anar.ro	0756 922 44	
Nădăru Adrian	ANAR	adrian.nadaru@anar.ro	0765 660 521	
LUTA DANIEL	ANAR	daniel.luta@anar.ro	0745 138 38	
Nita Roxandra	ANAR	roxandra.nita@anar.ro	0737 166 417	
Codrus Larisa Mihaela	ANAR	larisa.codrus@anar.ro	0737 166 417	
APOSTU AMELIA	ANAR	AMELIA.APOSTU@anar.ro	0723 661 115	
MOLDOVAN CONSTANȚA	ANAR	constanta.moldovan@anar.ro	0757 069 253	
FLORENTINA FLORENTINA	ANAR	florentina.florentina@anar.ro	0737 166 417	
SACIU DANIELA	ANAR	dana.saciu@anar.ro	0751 069 241	

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Leadership in Enabling and Industrial Technologies - Space programme under grant agreement No 730109

Figure 6. List of assistants in Romanian meeting.

END OF THE DOCUMENT

